

Checklist of the herpetofauna in an area of the Cerrado Biome, Central Brazil, under strong mining pressure

Fidélis Júnio Marra Santos

NeoGene, Goiânia, Goiás, Brazil

Email: fidelismarra@gmail.com

Received: 13 September 2024 / Revised: 31 October 2024 / Accepted: 31 October 2024 / Published online: 01 November 2024.

How to cite: Marra Santos, F.J. (2024). Checklist of the herpetofauna in an area of the Cerrado Biome, Central Brazil, under strong mining pressure, *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity*, 9(1), 332-354. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14635216>

Abstract

This study presents a checklist of amphibian and reptile species from a Cerrado area in the municipality of Minaçu, Goiás, central Brazil. Data were obtained during fauna rescue operations conducted during the construction of an access road for a mining enterprise. A total of 14 amphibian and 45 reptile species were recorded across three distinct phytophysiognomies (*Mata Seca*, *Mata de Galeria*, and *Mata Ciliar*) and an anthropogenic area characterized by pastures. In addition to the inventory, data on species richness and similarity among these four environments are presented.

Keywords: Central Brazil, Herpetofauna, Environmental licensing, Fauna rescue, Species richness.

Introduction

Brazil encompasses six major biomes: Amazon Rainforest, Cerrado, Atlantic Forest, Caatinga, Pantanal, and Pampa. Their geographical distribution is primarily driven by climatic factors—temperature, rainfall, and relative humidity—and, to a lesser extent, by soil substrate (Ribeiro & Walter, 1998). The Cerrado, located on the Brazilian Central Plateau, is the country's second-largest biome, covering over 2,000,000 km² (approximately 23% of the national territory). This vegetational complex shares ecological and physiognomic affinities with other tropical savannas in South America, Africa, and Australia (Beard, 1953; Cole, 1958; Eiten, 1972, 1994; Allem & Valls, 1987). Elevational ranges vary from 300 m in the Baixada Cuiabana (MT) to over 1,600 m

in the Chapada dos Veadeiros (GO). Ribeiro and Walter (1998) describe eleven main phytophysiognomic types within the Cerrado, categorized into forest formations (e.g., *Mata Ciliar*, *Mata de Galeria*, *Mata Seca*, and *Cerradão*), savanna formations (*Cerrado sentido restrito*, *Parque de Cerrado*, *Palmeiral*, and *Vereda*), and grasslands (*Campo Sujo*, *Campo Rupestre*, and *Campo Limpo*), many of which have subtypes. This study focuses on the herpetofauna of three forest formations—*Mata Seca*, *Mata de Galeria*, and *Mata Ciliar*—as well as an anthropic area characterized by pastures.

The Cerrado is one of the 25 global biodiversity hotspots, harboring one of the world's highest levels of richness and endemism for amphibians and reptiles (Myers et al., 2000). On a broader scale, Brazil maintains the most diverse herpetofauna globally, with each morphoclimatic domain supporting a unique evolutionary history (Neves et al., 2019). The herpetofauna of the Cerrado has been extensively documented by several authors (Colli et al., 2002; Vaz-Silva et al., 2007; Araujo & Almeida-Santos, 2011; Neves et al., 2019; Fiorillo et al., 2021; Guerra et al., 2022). This study provides a checklist of species recorded during fauna rescue operations associated with land clearing for road construction in Minaçu, Goiás, a region under significant anthropogenic pressure from mining activities. Alongside the checklist, species richness was analyzed using individual-based rarefaction to compare observed and expected richness. Furthermore, multivariate analyses were performed to assess herpetofaunal similarity among the three phytophysiognomies and the anthropogenic area.

Material and methods

Study area

The fauna rescue was conducted in the municipality of Minaçu, state of Goiás, Brazil (Fig. 1A), during road improvement works on an access route to a mining area (Fig. 1B). Monitoring and rescue operations took place along a 20-km stretch of the road and its adjacent areas (Fig. 1B). Minaçu is located in northern Goiás within the Tocantins-Araguaia Hydrographic Basin (Upper Tocantins Region), with the Tocantins River as the main watercourse. The region encompasses several Cerrado phytophysiognomies, such as *Cerradão*, *Campo Rupestre*, *Cerrado sentido restrito*, *Mata Ciliar*, *Mata de Galeria*, and *Mata Seca*; however, amphibians and reptiles were specifically recorded in the three forest formations (*Mata Ciliar*, *Mata de Galeria*, and *Mata Seca*) and in an anthropic area characterized by pastures. Geographic coordinates for all records were

obtained *in situ* using a Garmin eTrex 30 GPS. Recording points were subsequently plotted using Google Earth Pro v. 7.3.6, and the final map was generated using ArcMap (ArcGIS) v. 10.4.1, based on the WGS 1984 geodetic datum.

Figure 1. Study area. **A.** Location of the municipality of Minaçu, northern state of Goiás, Brazil, highlighting the study area and herpetofaunal record points (red dots). **B.** Detail of the road alignment monitored during land clearing operations, showing the distribution of herpetofaunal records. Yellow line = road route; red dots = reptiles; blue dots = amphibians.

Amphibian and reptile records

The herpetofauna checklist presented here resulted from fauna rescue operations conducted from May 10, 2019, to October 28, 2019. Animals were captured under license SECIMA 66208/2019 through active searches at the vegetation clearing fronts (Fig. 2). Most individuals were subsequently relocated to release points distant from the suppression areas. Individuals found dead due to heavy machinery operations were preserved and deposited as voucher specimens in the Coleção Herpetológica do Centro de Estudos e Pesquisas Biológicas at the Pontifícia Universidade Católica de Goiás (CEPB). A detailed list of these vouchers is provided in Appendix 1.

Species richness and similarity analyses were performed using PAST software v. 4.16c (Hammer et al., 2001). Individual-based rarefaction and the Chao-1 estimator were employed to compare observed and expected richness. Furthermore, a cluster analysis based on species abundance (using the Bray-Curtis index) was conducted to assess herpetofaunal similarity among the three sampled phytophysionomies and the anthropogenic area.

Figure 2. Fauna rescue operations during vegetation clearing at the mining enterprise access road in the municipality of Minaçu, northern state of Goiás, Brazil, showing the monitoring of heavy machinery activities to capture displaced individuals (Photo: Edilson Pires).

Results

Species composition

A total of 14 amphibian species (Fig. 3) and 45 reptile species (Figs. 6–8) were recorded in the study area. Amphibians were represented by two orders and six families: Anura — Bufonidae (1 species), Hylidae (4 species), Leptodactylidae (6 species), Microhylidae (1 species), and Odontophrynidae (1 species); and Gymnophiona — Siphonopidae (1 species) (Table 1, Fig. 4). Regarding reptiles, two orders (Squamata and Testudines) and 15 families were recorded. Within Squamata, families included Amphisbaenidae (4 species), Anolidae (1 species), Gymnophthalmidae (3 species), Hoplocercidae (1 species), Iguanidae (1 species), Phyllodactylidae (1 species), Polychrotidae (1 species), Scincidae (2 species), Teiidae (4 species), Tropiduridae (1 species), and the snake families Boidae (2 species), Colubridae (20 species), Leptotyphlopidae (1 species), and Viperidae (2 species); the order Testudines was represented by Testudinidae (1 species) (Table 3, Fig. 9).

Individual-based rarefaction of the amphibian community across the entire study area, combined with the Chao-1 estimator, revealed a total observed richness of 14 species from a sampling effort of 45 specimens ($N = 45$, $S_{obs} = 14$). The non-asymptotic shape of the cumulative curve indicates that the sampling plateau has not yet been reached, supporting the total estimated richness of 32 species predicted by the Chao-1 estimator and suggesting a high number of rare species in the region (see Table 5 and Figure 11). Regarding β -diversity, multivariate analysis of amphibian species similarity showed the highest values between the two driest environments (anthropogenic pasture and *Mata Seca*) and between the two riparian forest formations (*Mata de Galeria* and *Mata Ciliar*). Detailed similarity indices and cluster analyses are provided in Table 2 and Figure 5.

For the reptile community, the combination of individual-based rarefaction and the Chao-1 estimator revealed a total observed richness of 45 species across the entire study area. The shape of the cumulative curve indicates that the sampling plateau has been closely approached or reached, demonstrating high sampling efficiency for this group across the integrated enterprise area (see Table 5 and Figure 12). Regarding β -diversity, multivariate analysis of reptile similarity across the four sampled areas revealed the highest affinity between the two driest environments (*Mata Seca* and the anthropogenic pasture area). These two habitats also showed greater similarity to the *Mata de Galeria* phytophysiognomy. In contrast, *Mata Ciliar* was the least similar to the other three areas (Fig. 10). Detailed similarity indices for all comparisons are presented in Table 4.

Table 1. Checklist of amphibian species recorded during fauna rescue operations in the Cerrado of Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. Habitats: ANT/PAS (anthropic pasture area), MTS (*Mata Seca*), MTG (*Mata de Galeria*), and MTC (*Mata Ciliar*).

TAXON	ABUNDANCE BY HABITATS				TOTAL ABUNDANCE
	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC	
Amphibia					
Order Anura					
Suborder Neobatrachia					
Family Bufonidae					
<i>Rhinella diptycha</i> (Cope, 1862)	-	-	-	3	3
Family Hylidae					
<i>Boana raniceps</i> (Cope, 1862)	-	-	1	-	1
<i>Pithecopus hypochondrialis</i> (Daudin, 1800)	2	9	-	-	11
<i>Scinax fuscovarius</i> (Lutz, 1925)	1	1	1	-	3
<i>Trachycephalus typhonius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	1	-	-	1
Family Leptodactylidae					
<i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i> (Schneider, 1799)	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Leptodactylus latrans</i> (Steffen, 1815)	1	7	1	1	10
<i>Leptodactylus mystaceus</i> (Spix, 1824)	-	1	1	1	3
<i>Leptodactylus mystacinus</i> (Burmeister, 1861)	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Physalaemus cuvieri</i> (Fitzinger, 1826)	-	1	1	-	2
<i>Physalaemus nattereri</i> (Steindachner, 1863)	1	1	-	1	3
Family Microhylidae					

TAXON	ABUNDANCE BY HABITATS				TOTAL ABUNDANCE
	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC	
<i>Dermatonotus muelleri</i> (Boettger, 1885)	1	3	-	-	4
Family Odontophrynidae					
<i>Proceratophrys goyana</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	-	-	1	-	1
Order Gymnophiona					
Family Siphonopidae					
<i>Siphonops paulensis</i> Boettger, 1892	-	1	-	-	1

Figure 3. Representative amphibian species recorded in the Cerrado area during vegetation clearing for road construction. Bufonidae: (1) *Rhinella diptycha*; Hylidae: (2) *Boana raniceps*, (3) *Pithecopus hypochondrialis*; Leptodactylidae: (4) *Leptodactylus latrans*, (5) *Leptodactylus mystaceus*, (6) *Leptodactylus mystacinus*, (7) *Physalaemus nattereri*, (8) *Physalaemus cuvieri*; Microhylidae: (9) *Dermatophrynus muelleri*; Odontophrynidae: (10) *Proceratophrys goyana*. (Photos: Fidélis Júnio Marra Santos).

Figure 4. Species richness and abundance per amphibian family recorded during fauna rescue operations in Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. Blue bars represent richness (number of species) and orange bars represent abundance (total number of individuals).

Table 2. Similarity matrix (Bray-Curtis index) for amphibian species across the four sampled areas in Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. Values closer to 1 indicate higher similarity in species composition and abundance. ANT/PAS: anthropic pasture area; MTS: *Mata Seca*; MTG: *Mata de Galeria*; MTC: *Mata Ciliar*.

	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC
ANT/PAS	1.00			
MTS	0.36	1.00		
MTG	0.33	0.24	1.00	
MTC	0.33	0.18	0.33	1.00

Figure 5. Similarity dendrogram (Bray-Curtis index) of amphibian communities across the four sampled areas in Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. The cluster analysis was performed using the Unweighted Pair-Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (UPGMA) algorithm. ANT/PAS: anthropic pasture area; MTS: *Mata Seca*; MTG: *Mata de Galeria*; MTC: *Mata Ciliar*.

Table 3. Checklist of reptile species recorded during fauna rescue operations in the Cerrado of Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. Habitats: ANT/PAS (anthropic pasture area), MTS (*Mata Seca*), MTG (*Mata de Galeria*), and MTC (*Mata Ciliar*).

TAXON	ABUNDANCE BY HABITATS				TOTAL ABUNDANCE
	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC	
Reptilia					
Order Squamata					
Suborder Amphisbaenia					
Family Amphisbaenidae					
<i>Amphisbaena alba</i> Linnaeus, 1758	2	-	-	-	2
<i>Amphisbaena anaemariae</i> Vanzolini, 1997	8	17	9	7	41
<i>Amphisbaena fuliginosa</i> Linnaeus, 1758	2	7	-	-	9
<i>Leposternon infraorbitale</i> (Berthold, 1859)	-	1	1	-	2
Suborder Sauria					
Family Anolidae					
<i>Anolis brasiliensis</i> Vanzolini & Williams, 1970	-	-	4	-	4
Family Gymnophthalmidae					
<i>Cercosaura schreibersii</i> Wiegmann, 1834	-	1	4	-	5
<i>Colobosaura modesta</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	1	1	21	-	23
<i>Micrablepharus maximiliani</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	9	2	34	-	45
Family Hoplocercidae					
<i>Hoplocercus spinosus</i> Fitzinger, 1843	-	2	-	-	2
Family Iguanidae					

TAXON	ABUNDANCE BY HABITATS				TOTAL ABUNDANCE
	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC	
<i>Iguana iguana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2	4	-	1	7
Family Phyllodactylidae					
<i>Gymnodactylus amarali</i> Barbour, 1925	11	14	-	-	25
Family Polychrotidae					
<i>Polychrus acutirostris</i> Spix, 1825	2	10	-	-	12
Family Scincidae					
<i>Copeoglossum nigropunctatum</i> (Spix, 1825)	3	5	1	-	9
<i>Notomabuya frenata</i> (Cope, 1862)	6	20	2	1	29
Family Teiidae					
<i>Ameiva ameiva</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	5	27	6	1	39
<i>Ameivula ocellifera</i> (Spix, 1825)	15	16	-	1	32
<i>Salvator merianae</i> Duméril & Bibron, 1839	3	7	-	-	10
<i>Tupinambis quadrilineatus</i> Manzani & Abe, 1997	-	1	-	-	1
Family Tropiduridae					
<i>Tropidurus oreadicus</i> Rodrigues, 1987	1	6	-	2	9
Suborder Serpentes					
Family Boidae					
<i>Boa constrictor</i> Linnaeus, 1758	2	1	-	-	3
<i>Epicrates cenchria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	2	-	-	2

TAXON	ABUNDANCE BY HABITATS				TOTAL ABUNDANCE
	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC	
Family Colubridae					
<i>Adelphostigma occipitalis</i> (Jan, 1863)	1	2	-	1	4
<i>Apostolepis adhara</i> França et al., 2018	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Apostolepis sanctaeritae</i> Werner, 1924	1	-	1	1	3
<i>Chironius flavolineatus</i> (Boettger, 1885)	-	1	1	-	2
<i>Chironius quadricarinatus</i> (Boie, 1827)	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Dipsas bucephala</i> (Shaw, 1802)	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Dipsas mikanii</i> (Schlegel, 1837)	-	3	2	-	5
<i>Drymoluber brazili</i> (Gomes, 1918)	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Dryophylax phoenix</i> (Franco et al., 2017)	1	1	-	-	2
<i>Erythrolamprus almadensis</i> (Wagler, 1824)	-	2	2	-	4
<i>Erythrolamprus poecilogyrus</i> (Wied-Neuwied, 1824)	-	1	-	-	1
<i>Erythrolamprus reginae</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	2	-	-	2
<i>Leptodeira annulata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	-	-	1	1
<i>Oxyrhopus guibei</i> Hoge & Romano, 1977	1	10	-	-	11
<i>Oxyrhopus trigeminus</i> Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854	3	7	-	-	10
<i>Oxyrhopus rhombifer</i> Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854	1	2	-	-	3
<i>Philodryas nattereri</i> (Steindachner, 1870)	1	5	-	-	6
<i>Phimophis guerini</i> (Duméril, Bibron & Duméril, 1854)	1	4	-	-	5

TAXON	ABUNDANCE BY HABITATS				TOTAL ABUNDANCE
	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC	
<i>Spilotes pullatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	-	1	1	-	2
<i>Xenodon merremii</i> (Wagler, 1824)	-	4	-	-	4
Family Leptotyphlopidae					
<i>Trilepida koppesi</i> (Amaral, 1955)	-	6	-	-	6
Family Viperidae					
<i>Bothrops moojeni</i> Hoge, 1966	-	2	-	-	2
<i>Bothrops neuwiedi</i> Wagler, 1824	-	1	-	-	1
Order Testudines					
Suborder Cryptodira					
Family Testudinidae					
<i>Chelonoidis carbonarius</i> (Spix, 1824)	1	-	-	-	1

Figure 6. Representative reptile species (Amphisbaenia and Sauria) recorded in the Cerrado area during vegetation suppression for road construction. Amphisbaenidae: (1) *Amphisbaena alba*, (2) *Amphisbaena anaemariae*, (3) *Amphisbaena fuliginosa*, (4) *Leposternon infraorbitale*; Anolidae: (5) *Anolis brasiliensis*; Gymnophthalmidae: (6) *Cercosaura schreibersii*, (7) *Colobosaura modesta*, (8) *Micrablepharus maximiliani*; Hoplocercidae: (9) *Hoplocercus spinosus*; Iguanidae: (10) *Iguana iguana*; Phyllodactylidae: (11) *Gymnodactylus amarali*; Polychrotidae: (12) *Polychrus acutirostris*. (Photos: Fidélis Júnio Marra Santos).

Figure 7. Representative reptile species (Sauria and Serpentes) recorded in the Cerrado area during vegetation suppression for road construction. Scincidae: (13) *Copeoglossum nigropunctatum*, (14) *Notomabuya frenata*; Teiidae: (15) *Ameiva ameiva*, (16) *Ameivula ocellifera*, (17) *Salvator merianae*, (18) *Tupinambis quadrilineatus*; Tropiduridae: (19) *Tropidurus oreadicus*; Boidae: (20) *Boa constrictor*, (21) *Epicrates cenchria*; Colubridae: (22) *Apostolepis sanctaeritae*, (23) *Apostolepis adhara*, (24) *Chironius flavolineatus*. (Photos: Fidélis Júnio Marra Santos).

Figure 8. Representative reptile species (Serpentes and Testudines) recorded in the Cerrado area during vegetation suppression for road construction. Colubridae: (25) *Dipsas mikanii*, (26) *Leptodeira annulata*, (27) *Adelphostigma occipitalis*, (28) *Oxyrhopus trigeminus*, (29) *Oxyrhopus rhombifer*, (30) *Philodryas nattereri*, (31) *Xenodon merremii*, (32) *Dryophylax phoenix*; Leptotyphlopidae: (33) *Trilepida koppesi*; Testudinidae: (34) *Chelonoidis carbonarius*. (Photos: Fidélis Júnio Marra Santos).

Figure 9. Species richness and abundance per reptile family recorded during fauna rescue operations in Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. Blue bars represent richness (number of species) and orange bars represent abundance (total number of individuals).

Table 4. Similarity matrix (Bray-Curtis index) for reptile species across the four sampled areas in Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. Values closer to 1 indicate higher similarity in species composition and abundance. ANT/PAS: anthropic pasture area; MTS: *Mata Seca*; MTG: *Mata de Galeria*; MTC: *Mata Ciliar*.

	ANT/PAS	MTS	MTG	MTC
ANT/PAS	1.00			
MTS	0.50	1.00		
MTG	0.32	0.21	1.00	
MTC	0.28	0.13	0.19	1.00

Figure 10. Similarity dendrogram (Bray-Curtis index) of reptile communities across the four sampled areas in Minaçu, Goiás, Brazil. The cluster analysis was performed using the Unweighted Pair-Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (UPGMA) algorithm. ANT/PAS: anthropic pasture area; MTS: *Mata Seca*; MTG: *Mata de Galeria*; MTC: *Mata Ciliar*.

Table 5. Observed and estimated richness (Chao-1) for the herpetofauna in the study area.

Group	Observed Richness (S_{obs})	Estimated Richness (Chao-1)	Sampling Efficiency (%)
Amphibians	14	32	44%
Reptiles	45	49	92%

Figure 12. Individual-based rarefaction curve for the reptile community in the study area. The red line represents the cumulative number of species observed as a function of the number of sampled specimens ($N = 390$, $S_{obs} = 45$). The light blue shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval. The clear tendency toward an asymptotic shape at the end of the curve reflects a highly robust sampling effort, which aligns with the high sampling efficiency (92%) and the total estimated richness of 49 species predicted by the Chao-1 estimator.

Discussion

Sampling Efficiency and Habitat Heterogeneity

Individual-based rarefaction analysis and richness estimators revealed significant contrasts in faunal detectability across the study area. The fact that the reptile community closely approached its sampling plateau indicates that the fauna rescue operations were highly efficient in surveying this group within the integrated enterprise matrix. Conversely, the substantial gap between observed and expected richness for amphibians suggests that the regional sampling effort for this group remains incomplete, leaving a high estimated number of undetected species. This discrepancy highlights that while vegetation suppression methods are highly effective for conspicuous or terrestrial reptiles, they may undersample amphibian diversity. Riparian formations (*Mata de Galeria* and *Mata Ciliar*) and environments with watercourses likely harbor cryptic, canopy-dwelling, or semi-aquatic species whose habits prevent them from being fully captured solely by rescue methods during heavy machinery activities.

Similarity Patterns and Beta Diversity

Bray-Curtis similarity patterns demonstrate a strong structuring of the herpetofauna linked to the moisture gradient across the study area. The high affinity between the anthropogenic pasture and *Mata Seca* indicates a shared heliophilic fauna adapted to periods of water stress, a pattern particularly pronounced in reptile communities. On the other hand, the uniqueness of the *Mata Ciliar* for reptiles—which emerged as the least similar area to all others—highlights its importance as a biodiversity refuge and a zone of high species turnover (β -diversity) within the regional landscape. Additionally, the observed connectivity between riparian areas for amphibians reinforces the dependence of these organisms on humid corridors for dispersal.

Conservation Implications

These results reinforce that while anthropogenically altered areas present more homogeneous and easily sampled communities, forest and riparian formations hold the greatest potential for undocumented biodiversity. The discrepancy between observed and expected richness for riparian forests indicates that the impact of road construction in these areas may be underestimated if based solely on observed richness. Consequently, this underscores the need for rigorous mitigation measures to preserve cryptic or low-detectability taxa that were not directly recorded during the rescue but are statistically expected to be present.

The herpetofauna checklist presented here covers a period of just over five months and is the result of fauna rescue operations during the initial stage of construction for a mining company access road, where the entire route was followed from its origin on the GO-241 highway to its terminus along the banks of the Cana Brava River. Thus, the species richness data presented here should not be considered definitive, as future studies incorporating temporal variations and specialized sampling efforts focused on herpetofauna will likely record additional species not captured during this rescue phase. At the same time, the Cerrado within Minaçu is currently experiencing intense anthropogenic pressure due to mining activities. Habitat loss and potential contaminants associated with mining may exert negative pressures on local amphibian and reptile populations.

With over 4,800 endemic plant and vertebrate species, the Cerrado is a global biodiversity hotspot (Strassburg et al., 2017). Although mining is vital for socioeconomic development and serves as a crucial sector for the state economy, its environmental impacts on biodiversity cannot be underestimated (Rehman et al., 2021). Mineral exploitation threatens wildlife through soil and water contamination, vegetation suppression, and landscape fragmentation (Martins-Oliveira et al., 2021).

The local economic benefits of mining enterprises are evident in terms of employment and financial growth, but the corresponding impact on biodiversity must not be disregarded. Therefore, continuous monitoring of the region's herpetofauna is essential to establish a robust database capable of supporting effective conservation strategies.

Acknowledgments

I thank the editorial office of the *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity* and the anonymous reviewers for their valuable suggestions and support during the peer-review process of this manuscript. I am grateful to DBO Engenharia Ambiental (Goiás, Brazil) for logistical support during field activities. Finally, I would like to thank Dr. Wilian Vaz-Silva and his collaborators for their assistance with the specimen data deposited in the Coleção Herpetológica do Centro de Estudos e Pesquisas Biológicas da Pontifícia Universidade Católica de Goiás (CEPB), Goiânia, Brazil.

Author ORCID

Fidélis Júnio Marra Santos <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5140-2830>

References

- Araujo, C.O., & Almeida-Santos, S.M. (2011). Herpetofauna de um remanescente de cerrado no estado de São Paulo, sudeste do Brasil. *Biota Neotropica* 11 (3): 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1676-06032011000300003>
- Allem, A.C., & Valls, J.F.M. (1987). Recursos forrageiros nativos do Pantanal Mato-Grossense. EMBRAPA-CENARGEN, Brasília, Brasil, 339 pp.
- Beard, J.S. (1953). The savanna vegetation of northern tropical America. *Ecological Monographs* 23 (2): 149–215. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1948518>
- Cole, M.M. (1958). A Savana Brasileira. *Boletim Carioca de Geografia* 11: 5–52.
- Colli, G.R., Bastos, R.P., & Araujo, A.F.B. (2002). The Character and Dynamics of the Cerrado Herpetofauna. In: Oliveira, P.S., Marquis, R.J. (Eds.) *The cerrados of Brazil: ecology and natural history of a Neotropical Savanna*. Columbia University Press, New York, USA, 223–241. <https://doi.org/10.7312/oliv12042-011>
- Eiten, G. (1972). The Cerrado vegetation of Brazil. *Botanical Review* 38 (2): 201–341. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02859158>
- Eiten, G. (1994). Vegetação do Cerrado. In: Pinto, M.N. (Ed.) *Cerrado: caracterização, ocupação e perspectivas*. 2nd Edition. UnB/SEMATEC, Brasília, Brasil, 9–65.
- Fiorillo, B.F., Maciel, J.H., & Martins, M. (2021). Composition and natural history of a snake community from the southern Cerrado, southeastern Brazil. *ZooKeys* 1056: 95–147. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1056.63733>
- Guerra, V., Ramalho, W.P., Machado, I.F., & Brandão, R.A. (2022). Herpetofauna of the Serra do Tombador Nature Reserve, State of Goiás, Central Brazil. *Arquivos de Zoologia* 53 (3): 33–51. <https://doi.org/10.11606/2176-7793/2022.53.03>
- Hammer, Ø., Harper, D.A.T., & Ryan, P.D. (2001). PAST: Paleontological Statistics Software Package for Education and Data Analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 4 (1): 9 pp.
- Martins-Oliveira, A.T., Zanin, M., Canale, G.R., Costa, C.A., Eisenlohr, P.V., Melo, F.C.S.A., Melo, F.R. (2021). A global review of the threats of mining on mid-sized and large mammals. *Journal for Nature Conservation* 62: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2021.126025>
- Myers, N., Mittermeier, R.A., Mittermeier, C.G., Fonseca, G.A.B, Kent, J. (2000). Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities. *Nature* 403: 853–858. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35002501>

- Neves, M.O., Yves, A., Pereira, E.A., Alves, L., Vasques, J.B., Coelho, J.F.T., Silva, P.S. (2019). Herpetofauna in a highly endangered area: the Triângulo Mineiro region, in Minas Gerais State, Brazil. *Herpetozoa* 32: 113–123. <https://doi.org/10.3897/herpetozoa.32.e35641>
- Rehman, G., Khattak, I., Hamayun, M., Rahman, A., Haseeb, M., Umar, M., Ali, S., Iftikhar, M., Shams, W.A., Pervaiz, R. (2021). Impacts of mining on local fauna of wildlife in District Mardan & District Mohmand Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan. *Brazilian Journal of Biology* 84: 1–11. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1519-6984.251733>
- Ribeiro, J.F., Walter, B.M.T. (1998). Fitofisionomias do Bioma Cerrado. In: Sano, S.M., Almeida, S.P. (Eds.) *Cerrado: ambiente e flora*. EMBRAPA-CPAC, Planaltina, Brasil, 87–166.
- Strassburg, B., Brooks, T., Feltran-Barbieri, R., Iribarrem, A., Crouzeilles, R., Loyola, R., Latawiec, A.E., Filho, F.J.B.O., Scaramuzza, C.A.M., Scarano, F.R., Soares-Filho, B., Balmford, A. (2017). Moment of truth for the Cerrado hotspot. *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 1 (0099): 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0099>
- Vaz-Silva, W., Guedes, A., Aloísio, G., Azevedo-Silva, P., Barbosa, R., Gontijo, F., Oliveira, F. (2007). Herpetofauna, Espora Hydroelectric Power Plant, state of Goiás, Brazil. *Check List* 3 (4): 338–345. <https://doi.org/10.15560/3.4.338>

Appendix 1. Amphibians and reptiles from fauna rescue (Minaçu, GO) deposited in the CEPB/PUC Goiás Herpetological Collection.

Amphibia: *Scinax fuscovarius* (CEPB-10148); *Trachycephalus typhonius* (CEPB-10150).
Reptilia: Squamata: Amphisbaenia: *Amphisbaena alba* (CEPB-2392, 2399); *Amphisbaena anaemariae* (CEPB-2382, 2383, 2384, 2386, 2387, 2389, 2390, 2391, 2393, 2394, 2395, 2396, 2398, 2401, 2403, 2404, 2405, 2406, 2407, 2408, 2409, 2410, 2411, 2413, 2414); *Amphisbaena fuliginosa* (CEPB-2385, 2388, 2397, 2400, 2402, 2412). **Sauria:** *Ameiva ameiva* (CEPB-12269, 12270, 12272, 12274, 12276, 12277, 12278); *Ameivula ocellifera* (CEPB-12273, 12275); *Cercosaura schreibersii* (CEPB-12251); *Colobosaura modesta* (CEPB-12249); *Copeoglossum nigropunctatum* (CEPB-12263, 12264, 12265, 12268); *Gymnodactylus amarali* (CEPB-12260, 12261); *Hoplocercus spinosus* (CEPB-12252); *Iguana iguana* (CEPB-12253, 12254, 12255, 12256); *Micrablepharus maximiliani* (CEPB-12248, 12250); *Notomabuya frenata* (CEPB-12266, 12267); *Polychrus acutirostris* (CEPB-12262); *Salvator merianae* (CEPB-12271). **Serpentes:**

Adelphostigma occipitalis (CEPB-9277, 9292); *Apostolepis sanctaeritae* (CEPB-9279); *Boa constrictor* (CEPB-9264); *Bothrops neuwiedi* (CEPB-9296); *Chironius flavolineatus* (CEPB-9276); *Dipsas bucephala* (CEPB-9290); *Dipsas mikanii* (CEPB-9271); *Drymoluber brazili* (CEPB-9265); *Dryophylax phoenix* (CEPB-9283); *Erythrolamprus almadensis* (CEPB-9286); *Erythrolamprus reginae* (CEPB-9293); *Oxyrhopus guibei* (CEPB-9267, 9272, 9284, 9295); *Oxyrhopus trigeminus* (CEPB-9288, 9289, 9291); *Philodryas nattereri* (CEPB-9266, 9281, 9282); *Phimophis guerini* (CEPB-9268, 9270, 9285, 9294); *Spilotes pullatus* (CEPB-9269); *Trilepida koppesi* (CEPB-12257, 12258, 12259).